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Phosphorus Release Dynamics From Cover Crop Residues: A Comparison Between Single Species and Mixtures

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ABSTRACT

Cover crops (CCs) can help reduce soil erosion and promote nutrient cycling, and certain species are efficient phosphorus (P) miners. Upon incorporation into the soil, CCs biomass undergoes microbial mineralisation, releasing bioavailable P, potentially benefiting subsequent crops. However, the effects of the incorporation of single CC species residues compared to mixtures on soil P dissolution and mineralisation and release dynamics remain unknown. To investigate this, we incubated residues from seven CC species, seven 3-species mixtures, and one all-crops mixture at a P dose of 60 mg kg⁻¹ into a low-P, decalcified clayey chernozem soil for 45 days under controlled conditions. For comparison, a control (nil-P) and a triple superphosphate (TSP) treatment were included. Destructive sampling occurred at 5, 10, 15, 30, and 45 days post-incubation. Soils were analysed for pH, C:N ratio, potential phosphatase activity, P fractions, and microbial biomass P. CC mixtures reduced soil C:N ratios by up to 26% and increased the potential activity of alkaline phosphatase by up to 6.7-fold compared to the control. Phosphorus immobilisation was only observed under TSP, which more than doubled the moderately labile 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH inorganic P fraction. Microbial P did not change significantly under any amendment. While the C:N data suggested faster biomass decomposition in CC mixtures and promotion of P dissolution mechanisms, anion resin exchange P levels were comparable to those of the single CCs, with an overall average of 12.8 mg kg⁻¹, likely due to the soil's P buffering capacity. In conclusion, CC mixtures improved P-related parameters in the soil, but these changes were insufficient to promote higher P dissolution from biomass in a 45-day incubation period.

1 | Introduction

Cover crops (CCs) have been extensively investigated as a strategic tool to enhance phosphorus (P) cycling in agroecosystems, and can positively contribute to the main crop's yields and P uptake (Hallama et al. 2019). However, study outcomes

vary considerably, influenced by factors such as plant species and ecosystem functionality (Finney and Kaye 2017), soil biophysico-chemical properties (Rose et al. 2010), climatic conditions including temperature, humidity, and rainfall (Damon et al. 2014; Liu et al. 2019), agricultural management (Calegari et al. 2013), soil P status, soil P forms (Raniero and Santner 2024)

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and fertilisation practices (Teles et al. 2017), among other variables. This results in mixed reports on the benefits of cover cropping on P cycling and availability, ranging from highly positive, such as improving soil fertility and mycorrhizal colonisation of subsequent crops (Little et al. 2004; Njeru et al. 2014) to negative effects, such as P immobilisation and reduced availability in the short term (Damon et al. 2014; Almeida et al. 2019).

The fundamental mechanism underlying P cycling through cover cropping is based on the ability of some CC species to effectively solubilise and absorb soil P forms with low bioavailability (Soltangheisi et al. 2020; Honvault et al. 2021). This P-enriched biomass is then incorporated into the soil and undergoes microbial mineralisation, releasing plant-available orthophosphates into the soil solution (Chen et al. 2024) for succeeding cash crops (Varela et al. 2017). Understanding P cycling in agroecosystems is critical, given that P is an often-limiting nutrient in agriculture, as well as a finite and critical resource (Vitousek et al. 2010; Ågren et al. 2012; Scholz et al. 2013).

However, most studies on cover cropping are centred on their effects on soil C and N, often neglecting their implications in P cycling. Additionally, research often includes only single CC species, despite the widespread adoption of CC mixtures in practical scenarios (Elhakeem et al. 2019). The use of mixtures is justified primarily by evidence suggesting that employing multiple species offers a range of synergistic biological, chemical, and physical advantages compared to the individual effects of single species or leaving the land fallow (Elhakeem et al. 2019; Beillouin et al. 2021; Reiss and Drinkwater 2022). As examples, mixtures can promote positive interactions between rhizosphere acidification and mycorrhizal status on the activity of phosphatases, benefits to microbial community diversity and activity, and facilitative nutrient uptake interactions (Chen et al. 2019, 2022). Moreover, the diversity of plant residues incorporated into the soil can foster higher microbial diversity and activity, leading to faster soil organic matter (SOM) turnover (Drost et al. 2020), in agreement with the singular hypothesis of plant diversity (Naeem and Li 1997).

From an ecological perspective, mixtures more closely mimic natural plant communities, which are known to enhance ecosystem resilience through diversity-driven multifunctionality (Beillouin et al. 2021). A combination of CC species can optimise resource use with complementary traits, such as differing root architectures and nutrient uptake strategies. For instance, combining deep-rooted species with access to subsoil nutrients, and shallow-rooted species that capture surface nutrients, can result in an increase in nutrient recovery. Practically, mixtures offer farmers greater flexibility and adaptability to varying soil and climatic conditions. Growing multiple species increases the likelihood of successful CC establishment, even if certain mixture components face unfavourable growing conditions (Reiss and Drinkwater 2022).

Variations in the chemical composition and complexity of organic soil amendments can either enhance or inhibit decomposition rates depending on microbial activity and environmental conditions (Sinsabaugh et al. 2013; Gillis and Price 2016). However, there remains a notable gap in our comprehension of how single and mixed CC residues influence mineralisation patterns, P

solubilisation and soil P fractions, and impact on soil organic carbon (SOC) and total soil nitrogen (N_t). Studies on CC species like clovers (*Trifolium* sp., Frøseth et al. 2022), buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum*; Kumar et al. 2011), and others (Vogeler et al. 2022; White et al. 2022) reveal how variations in tissue structural composition and C:N ratios impact C and N mineralisation rates in soils. Despite the existence of significant contributions focusing on single CCs, this current study is, to the best of our knowledge, the first aiming to examine how the incorporation of tailored CC mixtures into the soil affects residue decomposition rates and soil C:N ratio, pH, phosphatase activity, P dissolution and mineralisation patterns, and P fractions in the short term compared to single species, a phosphate fertiliser, and fallow with no amendment.

We hypothesised that in comparison to their components' averages, single crops and fallow, the incorporation of mixed CC residues in soil would (1) reduce the soil C:N ratio by increasing N_t proportionally more than SOC, (2) accelerate P dissolution and mineralisation through increased phosphatase activity and pH decrease over time, and (3) increase P turnover, resulting in higher soil labile P levels over time. To investigate these hypotheses, we selected seven CC species known for their P mining/scavenging potential, such as high rhizosphere acidification potential, phosphatase exudation, mycorrhizal colonisation rates, root volume, and exudation of carboxylates (Hallama et al. 2019). These were buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum* Moench), white mustard (*Sinapis alba* L.), black oat (*Avena strigosa* Schreb.), linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.), ramtil (*Guizotia abyssinica* [L.] Cass.), berseem clover (*Trifolium alexandrinum* L.), and phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia* Benth.). From those, seven 3-crop CC mixtures and a mixture containing all species were tailored based on previous results (Raniero and Santner 2024). These crops were grown on, and their dry biomass was incubated into a low-P decalcified clayey chernozem and kept under controlled conditions for 45 days. Through destructive sampling, we analysed the short-term effects of these amendments on soil pH, potential phosphatase activity, soil C and N, and organic and inorganic P fractions.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Soil Collection and Analyses

The soil used in this experiment was a clayey chernozem (IUSS Working Group 2015), collected from the topsoil layer (0–15 cm) of an arable field located in Langenlebar, Austria. Before establishment, the soil was analysed for pH (0.01 mol L⁻¹ CaCl₂) at a 1:2.5 soil: solution ratio (pH meter inoLabMulti 9620 IDS), total P (*aqua regia* digestion), Olsen-P (0.5 mol L⁻¹ NaHCO₃ pH 8.5), Olsen et al. (1954) and maximum water holding capacity (MWHC) according to the method by ISO (2019). These data are available in Table 1.

2.2 | Cover Crop Species and Characterisation

The CC species tested were buckwheat (*Fagopyrum esculentum* Moench), white mustard (*Sinapis alba* L.), black oat (*Avena strigosa* Schreb.), linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.), ramtil

(*Guizotia abyssinica* [Lf] Cass.), berseem clover (*Trifolium alexandrinum* L.), and phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia* Benth.). To obtain the biomass for the incubation, each species was individually cultivated in pots containing 2 kg of the experimental soil in a greenhouse (18°C–31°C). Plants were supplied with a nil-P nutrient solution (Table S1), and 30 mg P kg⁻¹ soil via triple superphosphate (TSP). Roots and shoots were collected at the pre-flowering stage, ensuring a more even P distribution across organs. Roots were washed with tap water to remove soil particles, and were then mixed together with shoots (within the same species) to simulate real production conditions, where both tissues are incorporated into the soil after CC termination. The biomass was dried in the oven at 65°C for 48 h and cut into 1 cm long pieces. Plant tissue subsamples were milled to <2 mm and microwave-digested using HNO₃ and H₂O₂. The P concentration of the digests was determined using ICP-OES (Optima 8300, PerkinElmer, Massachusetts, USA).

TABLE 1 | Soil characteristics prior to the incubation experiment.

Parameter	Unit	Value
pH _{CaCl2}	—	6.6
Maximum water holding capacity	mL kg ⁻¹	439
Total P	mg kg ⁻¹	679
Olsen-P	mg kg ⁻¹	3.42
Microbial biomass P	mg kg ⁻¹	14.9
CaCO ₃	mg kg ⁻¹	~0
Total C	g kg ⁻¹	25.6
Total inorganic C	g kg ⁻¹	~0
Soil organic C	g kg ⁻¹	25.0
Total N	g kg ⁻¹	2.53
C:N ratio	—	9.88
Sand	g kg ⁻¹	168
Silt	g kg ⁻¹	388
Clay	g kg ⁻¹	444

TABLE 2 | Properties of cover crop residues introduced in the soil as amendments.

Cover crop species	Abbreviation	C	N	P	WEP	C:N	C:P	N:P
		g kg ⁻¹ DM						
Buckwheat	BW	468	10.1	2.17	1.43 (65.7%)	46.3	216	4.65
Mustard	MT	451	22.3	1.77	1.29 (73.1%)	20.2	255	12.6
Black oat	BO	483	19.3	2.15	1.64 (76.1%)	25.0	225	8.98
Linseed	LS	501	27.2	2.49	1.87 (75.2%)	18.4	201	10.9
Ramtil	RT	409	19.6	2.23	1.67 (74.9%)	20.9	183	8.79
Berseem clover	BC	480	31.0	3.11	2.15 (69.2%)	15.5	154	9.97
Phacelia	PH	397	13.2	1.94	1.45 (74.8%)	30.1	205	6.80

Note: Values inside parenthesis represent the % in relation to the total tissue P concentration. Abbreviations: DM, dry matter; WEP, water-extractable P.

The water-extractable P (WEP) in the plant tissue was obtained using a modification of the method described by Hansen et al. (2022): 1 g of plant material (shoot plus root; milled to a powder) was extracted in 45 mL ultrapure water (laboratory grade type I, ≥ 18 MΩ cm) for 1 h and subsequently centrifuged and filtered (2.5 μm mesh filter). The WEP in the extracts was determined via the phospho-molybdate blue method (Murphy and Riley 1962). Plant C and N content were determined using a CN analyser (vario MACRO cube, Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Hanau, Germany). These data are shown in Table 2.

2.3 | Treatments

The treatments included the factors “amendment type” (no amendment (fallow), single CC biomass, CC mixtures and mineral fertiliser), and “incubation time” (sampling dates). For the amendments, biomass from the seven CC species was included individually. In addition, seven 3-species mixtures were tailored considering complementary P acquisition characteristics, aiming to combine plants which could potentially act synergistically in improving P cycling.

The mixture tailoring process was guided by potentially synergistic plant traits relevant to P cycling, including root biomass and architecture, rhizosphere acidification potential, phosphatase exudation, and P uptake efficiencies. This approach was informed by both empirical evidence observed for the species in (Raniero and Santner 2024), and by theoretical assumptions based on literature, which indicate complementary functional traits can enhance nutrient cycling and decomposition dynamics, and provide additional information on important P mobilisation traits (Joner and Johansen 2000; Jia et al. 2004; Brooker et al. 2008; Püschel et al. 2017; Elhakeem et al. 2019; Drost et al. 2020; Jansa and Hodge 2021; Jiang et al. 2021; Heuermann et al. 2022; Chen et al. 2022; Yu et al. 2024). In addition, experienced practitioners in central Europe were consulted to guarantee the feasibility of the use of these CC mixtures in real field conditions. This approach ensured that the mixtures were designed with both practical relevance and scientific rigour. Specific information about the mixture tailoring process can be seen in Data S1.

The mixtures included were: (1) black oat + linseed + rami (BO + LS + RT), (2) black oat + buckwheat + mustard (BO + BW + MT), (3) black oat + rami + mustard (BO + RT + MT), (4) linseed + phacelia + berseem clover (LS + PH + BC), (5) rami + phacelia + mustard (RT + PH + MT), (6) buckwheat + phacelia + berseem clover (BW + PH + BC), and (7) buckwheat + linseed + berseem clover. Additionally, a mixture containing all seven crops was also included (all-crops mixture).

To apply each treatment, the dry and cut (1 cm) biomass of single CCs and mixtures was added at a 60 mg kg⁻¹ P dose, which was selected for being a reasonable P application rate aiming at supplying crops needs in this soil type in central Europe. In the case of mixtures, equal contributions to the total P added (20 mg kg⁻¹ P per species) were applied, ensuring that each species contributed equally to the P added, allowing a balanced evaluation of P dynamics. Amendment application was standardised based on P dose to ensure consistent P input across treatments, allowing differences in P dissolution to reflect residue composition and decomposition dynamics rather than varying P content in the biomass. The CC treatments and amounts of plant tissue, C and N added are shown in Table S2. For comparison purposes, an unamended control (nil-P) and a fertilised control with 60 mg kg⁻¹ of P as TSP ground to a powder were also added.

2.4 | Incubation Setup

Plastic cups (300 mL) were filled with 150 g of dry soil sieved to <4 mm and adjusted to 30% MWHC with ultrapure water. The cups were covered with perforated parafilm to allow gas exchange and incubated in a climatic chamber at 25°C and 50% humidity for 7 days prior to the experiment to stimulate microbial activity before amendment incorporation. Destructive sampling was performed at days 5, 10, 15, 30, and 45 after biomass incorporation, balancing temporal resolution of P dynamics and the high effort, time, and resources required to manage all experimental steps and laboratory analyses. Each treatment had triplicates, and the unamended control included three additional replicates sampled after the initial water-only incubation (prior to biomass incorporation). These served as the starting point of the soil after initiating microbial activity (day 0), resulting in 258 experimental units.

After the treatments were applied, the biomass was thoroughly mixed into the soil using an end-over-end shaker for 30 min. The pots were adjusted to 60% MWHC, individually determined based on the variation of the biomass incorporation rates to achieve the target P dose. Pots were resealed with perforated parafilm, randomly placed in the climatic chamber, and maintained at 60% MWHC on a weight basis under a temperature cycle of 14/10 h at 25°C and 16°C, in the dark.

2.5 | Experimental Caveats and Limitations

2.5.1 | Biomass Incorporation Rate

For the experiment, an intentional high amount of dry CC residues was incorporated into the soil, which would represent values between 170 and 300 t ha⁻¹ on an area basis. This substantial

biomass input was intended to facilitate the investigation of fundamental mechanisms underlying P dissolution and mineralisation, clearly highlight the impact of the amendments and provide a detailed understanding of the processes involved. While such residue quantities exceed typical field-scale application rates, they are ecologically plausible in localised soil microsites characterised by high organic matter inputs, such as litter hotspots or the detritusphere (Kuzyakov and Blagodatskaya 2015; Loepmann et al. 2016; Kim et al. 2023). These zones often develop beneath dense plant patches or in areas of concentrated root turnover and can exhibit organic matter inputs several times greater than the surrounding bulk soil. The high residue: soil ratios used in this study aimed to simulate these biologically active hotspots, where microbial activity, nutrient cycling, and decomposition processes are intensified.

2.5.2 | Experimental Duration

The 45-day duration of the experiment was chosen to allow the study of the short-term dynamics of CC biomass incorporation into the soil and its immediate effects on soil P status. This timeframe allows for early biomass mineralisation and nutrient release, potentially making P available for the next crop. Therefore, our findings do not address long-term biomass decomposition or P dynamics, which would require further long-term investigations for a more comprehensive understanding.

2.5.3 | Soil Type

Our experimental design focuses on a single soil type: clayey chernozem, chosen for its agricultural importance across Europe, North America, and Asia. The chosen soil, with a SOM content of ~4.3% and a high clay content (44%), features stable aggregates and a relatively slow SOM turnover rate. While this selection allows for a detailed investigation of biomass decomposition and P dynamics under high-SOM, low-P conditions, we acknowledge that using a single soil type limits the broader applicability of our findings. However, expanding our experimental design to multiple soils would have significantly increased the experimental complexity, effort, and resource requirements.

2.5.4 | Controlled Conditions

Our experiment was conducted under controlled conditions of humidity, watering, particle sizes (soil and plant), and light deprivation, allowing us to isolate amendment effects and clearly observe their influence on soil P dynamics. In practical agricultural settings, various field factors can influence P release from amendments in ways that may differ from our observations. Soil heterogeneity, varying moisture regimes, temperature fluctuations, and microbial diversity can all impact decomposition rates and nutrient mineralisation. For instance, inconsistent soil moisture in the field could slow residue decomposition and P mineralisation, particularly under drought conditions. Conversely, wetter soils may accelerate microbial activity, potentially increasing P release but also raising the risk of P losses through leaching or runoff. Moreover, the biomass incorporation ratios used in field conditions are often more variable and

may influence the C:N balance, residue decomposition rates, and microbial activity differently than in our controlled setup. Soil texture and pH, which can vary significantly across sites, also play crucial roles in P sorption–desorption processes and, consequently, labile P availability (Ntonta et al. 2022). Therefore, our experiment was designed to observe effects under controlled conditions and may therefore not be directly translated to practical agricultural settings, considering different soils, biomass incorporation ratios, or field scenarios. It instead serves to elucidate fundamental nutrient cycling dynamics in an important soil type under controlled conditions.

2.6 | Analyses

At every sampling date, each replicate was split into subsamples (a) and (b). Subsample (a) was kept at original moisture, sieved (<4 mm) to remove coarse organic material, and was used for microbial biomass P (MBP) determination. For this, three subsamples (ai, aii, and aiii) were prepared as follows: subsample (ai) was kept in its original condition, (aii) underwent CHCl_3 fumigation at 25°C for 24 h in a desiccator, and (aiii) received an application (P spike) of 25 mg P kg⁻¹ soil as KH_2PO_4 to correct for P sorption (Brookes et al. 1982). Fumigant was removed from the desiccator by using a vacuum pump for 5 min. All samples were extracted by 0.5 mol L⁻¹ NaHCO_3 at pH 8.5 (Olsen et al. 1954), and extracts were analysed for P through the phospho-molybdate blue method (Murphy and Riley 1962). Subsample (a) was also used to measure the potential activity of acid (ACP_{ASE}) and alkaline (ALP_{ASE}) phosphatases, adjusting the method described by Tabatabai and Bremner (1969) as proposed by Daughtridge et al. (2021): after incubation at 21°C (mean climatic chamber temperature) with a p-nitrophenyl phosphate (Sigma N4645) buffered solution (pH 6.5 and 11, respectively), p-nitrophenol release (mg kg⁻¹ h⁻¹) was determined colorimetrically at 410 nm. For accurate control of abiotic hydrolysis, soil-only and substrate-only controls were included.

Subsample (b) was air-dried and sieved to 2 mm, removing all remaining coarse particulate organic matter (POM), and used for determining $\text{pH}_{\text{CaCl}_2}$, SOC, and N_t content in a CN analyser (vario MACRO cube, Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Hanau, Germany), and the first three extraction steps of the P fractionation described by Hedley et al. (1982). The fractionation extracts inorganic (P_i) and organic (P_o) P forms with decreasing bioavailability. Soils were sequentially extracted by an anion exchange resin (AER-P) in ultrapure water, 0.5 mol L⁻¹ NaHCO_3 solution at pH 8.5, and 0.1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH solution. After 16 h of shaking, samples were centrifuged, and the supernatant was analysed for P_i . The P_o in the alkaline extracts (NaHCO_3 and NaOH) was calculated as the difference between the total P in the extracts, obtained after $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + (\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ autoclave digestion, and the P_i . All P determinations were performed according to Murphy and Riley (1962).

2.7 | Statistical Analyses

All data were tested for normality with Q-Q plots. A two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed for each variable, considering the factors “incubation time” and “amendment

type.” Significant effects ($p \leq 0.05$) were followed by the Tukey’s honestly significant difference (HSD) test for post hoc comparisons. The calculated HSD values are represented as grey zones around the mixtures’ means in the figures, facilitating the comparison of any two means from day 5 onwards between mixtures and the unamended and fertilised controls. If a data point falls within the grey zone, they are not significantly different from the mixture value at the $p \leq 0.05$ significance level. The lines connecting data points serve as visual aid and do not represent the variable’s behaviour between sampling dates. All statistical analyses were conducted using the R software (version 4.2.1) and packages ggplot2 (Wickham, Chang, et al. 2024), Agricolae (de Mendiburu 2023), dplyr (Wickham, François, et al. 2020), and ggpubr (Kassambara 2023). To identify possible synergies of the CC mixtures, average values of the three crops composing the mixture were calculated and displayed for comparison but were not statistically tested, since they do not represent actual tested amendments.

The Tukey’s HSD was chosen instead of the often-applied LSD test due to its conservative nature, minimising type I errors. This approach ensures reliable comparisons given the variability of microbial and residue decomposition processes. Moreover, it supports balanced interpretations of P release dynamics, advancing understanding and guiding future research. All figures were drawn using the R software (version 4.2.1). To aid visualisation and interpretation, additional annotated figures are available in the Data S1.

3 | Results

3.1 | Soil Organic Carbon, Total Nitrogen, and C:N Ratio

All soils amended with plant residues exhibited substantial increases in SOC and N_t content (Figures S1 and S2), significantly surpassing the levels in both unamended and fertilised controls. Both controls showed no significant changes in SOC or N_t , averaging 2.3% and 0.25%, respectively, across all sampling dates. Single CCs and mixtures had varying impacts on SOC and N_t dynamics.

Generally, all CC amendments increased SOC within the first 30 days of incubation compared to the controls. Most single species treatments peaked in soil C levels on day 10, except for mustard and black oat, which peaked on day 30 with SOC contents reaching 5.5% and 4.9%, respectively, which are significantly higher than values at day 0 (2.3%). By day 45, only clover, phacelia, and the LS + PH + BC mixture had SOC levels comparable to those of the controls. Most CC mixtures behaved similarly to the average of their components, except for BO + LS + RT, BO + BW + MT, and BO + RT + MT, which showed SOC contents 25%, 32%, and 23% lower than the average of their components on day 30, respectively.

Additionally, single CCs significantly increased soil N_t levels above those of the controls as early as day 5, maintaining higher levels until the last sampling date for most species. Phacelia and clover were exceptions: phacelia caused an early N_t increase, peaking at 0.51% on day 10, then declining to control

FIGURE 1 | Soil C:N ratio over 45 days following amendment with single cover crop residues and their mixtures at a 60 mg kg⁻¹ P dose. The red dashed lines show the average values of the three single crops composing each mixture for comparison. The grey area represents HSD values, facilitating comparisons from day 5 onwards. Data points within the grey zone are not significantly different from the mixture value at $p \leq 0.05$. Lines connecting data points are for visual aid only.

levels by day 30; clover showed a moderate increase, reaching 0.39% on day 10, followed by a steady decline to control levels from day 30 onwards. Notably, mustard, black oat, and ramtil exhibited lower relative reductions in N_t after an initial increase compared to other single species. Buckwheat induced a small but consistent N_t increase throughout the incubation period, averaging 0.35% across all days. Soils amended with CC mixtures generally displayed higher absolute N_t levels on most sampling days compared to the averages of their components. The largest differences were observed on days 5 and 10 for BO + LS + RT; days 5, 10, and 45 for BW + LS + BC; day 30 for LS + PH + BC; and from day 15 onwards for RT + PH + MT and BW + PH + BC.

Due to the stability of SOC and N_t levels in both the unamended and TSP control treatments, their soil C:N ratio remained unchanged through the incubation, at an average \pm SD of 8.92 ± 0.35 . For mixture-amended soils, changes in SOC and N_t content resulted in significantly lower C:N ratios

in the soils when compared to the average of single crop components and, in many cases, also to the controls (Figure 1). While the unamended control average C:N ratio across the sampling dates was 8.95 ± 0.47 , the mixtures LS + PH + BC, BW + LS + BC, and the all-crop mixture consistently exhibited lower soil C:N ratios than their components' averages from day 5 onwards. Significantly lower C:N ratios in comparison to the unamended control were seen for BO + LS + RT on day 15, LS + PH + BC on day 5, RT + PH + MT on days 15 and 30, BW + PH + BC on day 30, and for the all-crops mixture on days 5 and 10.

3.2 | Soil pH

The unamended control maintained a constant pH throughout the incubation period, averaging at pH 6.63, which was significantly altered by the amendments (Figure 2). The TSP treatment initially acidified the soil, significantly reducing the pH to

FIGURE 2 | Soil pH over 45 days following amendment with single cover crop residues and their mixtures at a 60 mg kg⁻¹ P dose. The red dashed lines show the average values of the three single crops composing each mixture for comparison. The grey area represents HSD values, facilitating comparisons from day 5 onwards. Data points within the grey zone are not significantly different from the mixture value at $p \leq 0.05$. Lines connecting data points are for visual aid only.

6.16 ± 0.02 on day 5 and 6.21 ± 0.07 on day 10, before increasing to levels comparable to the control for the remainder of the incubation. All single CCs initially increased soil pH, which then shifted to an acidifying effect starting on day 10. Buckwheat and mustard never returned to the starting soil pH level, ending on day 45 with pH values of 7.43 ± 0.07 and 7.02 ± 0.08, respectively. Black oat was the only crop that did not initially alkalinise the soil, showing an acidifying effect compared to the control on days 15 and 30, and increasing the pH on day 45 to a level higher than the control.

The mixtures behaved differently from their components' averages. The most contrasting mixture, BO + BW + MT, exhibited a higher soil pH on day 15 than the average, which then decreased to significantly lower levels by day 45. All other mixtures promoted comparable or lower initial alkalinisation and comparable or higher late acidification compared to their components' averages. For instance, RT + PH + MT, BW + PH + BC, and BO + LS + RT showed similar or lower initial alkalinisation

levels. By day 45, the single crops clover and phacelia, along with the mixtures BO + RT + MT, LS + PH + BC, BW + PH + BC, and BW + LS + BC, had soil pH levels significantly lower than both controls.

3.3 | Potential Activity of Acid Phosphatases

No changes in the potential activity of ACP_{ASE} (Figure 3) were observed for the unamended control, which averaged at 116 ± 6.00 mg h⁻¹ kg⁻¹ throughout the incubation period. The TSP treatment was the only one to show a significant reduction in ACP_{ASE}, which was significantly lower than every other treatment starting from day 5 and remaining consistently low through the incubation, with a minimum value of 66.4 ± 3.53 mg h⁻¹ kg⁻¹ observed on day 10. The clover was the only single CC that had significantly higher ACP_{ASE} than the unamended control, with the highest value of all treatments, at 151 ± 15.4 mg h⁻¹ kg⁻¹ on day 45.

FIGURE 3 | Potential acid phosphatase activity (p-nitrophenol released in $\text{mg h}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$) over 45 days following amendment with single cover crop residues and their mixtures at a 60 mg kg^{-1} P dose. The red dashed lines show the average values of the three single crops composing each mixture for comparison. The grey area represents HSD values, facilitating comparisons from day 5 onwards. Data points within the grey zone are not significantly different from the mixture value at $p \leq 0.05$. Lines connecting data points are for visual aid only.

The mixtures largely behaved as the averages of their components. Only BW + LS + BC showed significantly higher ACP_{ASE} than the unamended control, and only on day 45. A trend for higher ACP_{ASE} values compared to their components' averages was observed for BO + RT + MT between days 15 and 30, BW + LS + BC from day 5 onwards, BO + LS + RT on day 5, and the all-crops mixture on days 15 and 30; however, without statistical significance.

3.4 | Potential Activity of Alkaline Phosphatases

The potential activity of ALP_{ASE} (Figure 4) of the unamended control remained steady throughout the entire incubation period, averaging at $75.4 \pm 3.44 \text{ mg h}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$. Similar to ACP_{ASE} , TSP was the only amendment that caused a reduction in ALP_{ASE} , maintaining a stable average of $30.8 \pm 9.39 \text{ mg h}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$ on every sampling date, significantly lower than the unamended control in a two-way ANOVA testing only the control against the TSP

treatment for the parameters “incubation time,” “amendment type,” and their interaction. However, unlike ACP_{ASE} , ALP_{ASE} was significantly increased by all CC amendments on every sampling date. The highest values were observed for buckwheat on day 10 ($500 \pm 8.05 \text{ mg h}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$), mustard on day 5 ($490 \pm 8.36 \text{ mg h}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$), and phacelia on day 10 ($477 \pm 31.4 \text{ mg h}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$). Buckwheat and phacelia maintained higher ALP_{ASE} levels than all other amendments until the end of the experiment, being significantly higher than mustard only on day 45, when mustard's ALP_{ASE} levels significantly dropped, becoming comparable to those of black oat, ramtil, and clover. The mixtures showed significant increases in the potential ALP_{ASE} in comparison to the controls and some single species, with the highest peaks observed by the all-crops mixture on days 30 and 45 (509.1 ± 6.03 and $509.0 \pm 16.7 \text{ mg h}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$, respectively). Except for BW + PH + BC, all other mixtures promoted significant increases in potential ALP_{ASE} activity compared to their components' averages starting as early as day 5. The exception was BO + BW + MT, where the increase began on day 15.

FIGURE 4 | Potential alkaline phosphatase activity (p-nitrophenol released in $\text{mg h}^{-1} \text{kg}^{-1}$) over 45 days following amendment with single cover crop residues and their mixtures at a 60 mg kg^{-1} P dose. The red dashed lines show the average values of the three single crops composing each mixture for comparison. The grey area represents HSD values, facilitating comparisons from day 5 onwards. Data points within the grey zone are not significantly different from the mixture value at $p \leq 0.05$. Lines connecting data points are for visual aid only.

3.5 | Soil Labile P Fractions

3.5.1 | Anion Exchange Resin Extractable P

Soil AER-P (Figure 5) remained unchanged in the unamended control, averaging at $5.84 \pm 0.25 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ throughout the entire incubation period. All amendments significantly increased AER-P compared to the control as early as day 5. On this day, the fertilised control averaged $24.2 \pm 1.23 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, the highest AER-P recorded during the entire incubation period and significantly higher than all CC amendments. After this initial spike, AER-P under TSP decreased on each subsequent sampling date, reaching its lowest value of $15.1 \pm 0.20 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ on day 45. Despite a reduction of over -37% in AER-P from days 5 to 45, TSP-amended soils consistently displayed the highest AER-P values across all treatments, matched only by clover and buckwheat on day 15 and by the all-crops mixture on day 45.

The highest AER-P levels for single CCs recorded on day 5 were achieved by clover ($15.6 \pm 0.54 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), ramtil ($14.6 \pm 0.96 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), and linseed ($14.1 \pm 0.16 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), which were comparable.

The clover AER-P was significantly higher than buckwheat ($13.0 \pm 1.27 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), mustard ($12.4 \pm 0.69 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), and black oat ($12.1 \pm 1.20 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), which were statistically equal. Phacelia was significantly lower than all single CCs on this day, at $9.38 \pm 0.69 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$. While ramtil peaked on day 5 and reached its minimum of $11.0 \pm 0.37 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ on day 30, clover peaked on day 15, and linseed on day 10, reaching AER-P values of $16.0 \pm 1.23 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ and $17.8 \pm 0.73 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, respectively. The mixtures exhibited behaviour similar to their components' averages, with no stark contrasts or statistical differences between AER-P levels on any sampling day.

3.5.2 | NaHCO_3 Extractable Inorganic P

The NaHCO_3 extractable inorganic P ($\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_i$, Figure 6) behaved similarly to the AER-P, with the control resting at an average of $4.28 \pm 0.31 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ and the TSP displaying an initial spike on day 5, reaching $16.4 \pm 1.13 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, the highest value observed for all treatments. Unlike AER-P, however, on day 45,

FIGURE 5 | Anion exchange resin extracted soil P (mg kg^{-1}) levels over 45 days following amendment with single cover crop residues and their mixtures at a 60 mg kg^{-1} P dose. The red dashed lines show the average values of the three single crops composing each mixture for comparison. The grey area represents HSD values, facilitating comparisons from day 5 onwards. Data points within the grey zone are not significantly different from the mixture value at $p \leq 0.05$. Lines connecting data points are for visual aid only.

soil $\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_i$ under TSP reached $10.9 \pm 0.36 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, falling significantly below that of linseed and clover, but being comparable to that of black oat, mustard, and all mixtures except $\text{RT} \pm \text{PH} \pm \text{MT}$, the only mixture which promoted significantly lower $\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_i$ ($8.15 \pm 0.27 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) than TSP on this day. While most single species displayed a peak in $\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_i$ between days 5 and 15 followed by a slight to sharp decrease, the buckwheat and the mustard were exceptions, showing a constant increase in $\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_i$ through the incubation's duration. In relation to their components, most mixtures displayed comparable or lower $\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_i$ on most sampling days. Exceptions were $\text{BO} \pm \text{BW} \pm \text{MT}$ on day 15, and the $\text{BW} \pm \text{PH} \pm \text{BC}$ and $\text{BW} \pm \text{LS} \pm \text{BC}$, which had higher $\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_i$ on days 5 and 45.

3.5.3 | NaHCO_3 Extractable Organic P

The 0.5 mol L^{-1} NaHCO_3 extractable organic P ($\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_o$, Figure 7) remained steady and comparable for both controls

throughout the incubation period, averaging $38.1 \pm 1.17 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$. Only ramtil and linseed did not show any significant increases in $\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_o$ levels on any sampling day relative to the unamended and fertilised controls, while clover showed only one significantly higher value on day 5. The buckwheat had significantly higher $\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_o$ than the controls on every sampling day, reaching a maximum of $44.0 \pm 2.09 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ on day 30. Phacelia had significantly higher $\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_o$ than the controls from day 15 onwards, while black oat and mustard were higher on the last two sampling days.

With the exception of $\text{BO} \pm \text{LS} \pm \text{RT}$, all other mixtures exhibited at least one significantly higher $\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_o$ value than the control within the first 15 days of the experiment, with $\text{BO} \pm \text{BW} \pm \text{MT}$ consistently showing higher levels during the initial third of the incubation period. By day 45, only the $\text{LS} + \text{PH} + \text{BC}$ and all-crops mixtures had significantly higher $\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_o$ levels than the control, reaching 42.8 ± 1.27 and $46.3 \pm 1.94 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, respectively. All other mixtures showed a

FIGURE 6 | Soil NaHCO_3 0.5 mol L^{-1} extracted inorganic P (mg kg^{-1}) levels over 45 days following amendment with single cover crop residues and their mixtures at a 60 mg kg^{-1} P dose. The red dashed lines show the average values of the three single crops composing each mixture for comparison. The grey area represents HSD values, facilitating comparisons from day 5 onwards. Data points within the grey zone are not significantly different from the mixture value at $p \leq 0.05$. Lines connecting data points are for visual aid only.

significant reduction, sometimes falling well below the component averages.

The sum of the labile P fractions (AER-P, $\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}_i$ and -P_o) can be considered the soil labile P pool (Figure 8), which remained steady for the unamended control ($48.5 \pm 1.00 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), but was significantly increased under every amendment. For the labile P pool, a similar behaviour to that of the AER-P fraction was observed, in which TSP promoted an initial P spike on day 5, reaching $77.9 \pm 2.28 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, significantly higher than every CC amendment, and reduced over time, reaching a labile P value of $63.9 \pm 1.55 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ on day 45, statistically comparable to that of all single CCs and three-crops mixtures on this day. The exception was the all-crops mixture, which had a labile P value of $70.6 \pm 0.27 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ on day 45, significantly higher than TSP. Interestingly, the all-crops mixture was the only amendment to promote increasing labile P concentrations on every sampling date, with no labile P reductions observed through the duration of the trial.

In general, the mixtures differed from single crops in labile P release by exhibiting variable labile P dynamics, with some crops (e.g., clover and linseed) showing a sharper initial increase followed by a decrease, while others (e.g., buckwheat and mustard) showed a more stable P release behaviour over time. Mixtures, on the other hand, showed a more sustained P release, rather than sharp peaks and declines observed in some single crops. Initial labile P peaks (day 5) are often statistically comparable between mixtures and their highest-contributing component, but mixtures tend to stabilise labile P levels over time compared to the more fluctuating single crop responses. Only the mixture BO+BW + MT showed a statistically lower labile P at day 5 compared to its highest-contributing component, the mustard.

3.6 | NaOH Extractable Inorganic and Organic P

The 0.1 mol L^{-1} NaOH extractable inorganic P (NaOH-P_i , Figure S3) remained largely unaffected by both single and

FIGURE 7 | Soil NaHCO_3 0.5 mol L^{-1} extracted organic P (mg kg^{-1}) levels over 45 days following amendment with single cover crop residues and their mixtures at a 60 mg kg^{-1} P dose. The red dashed lines show the average values of the three single crops composing each mixture for comparison. The grey area represents HSD values, facilitating comparisons from day 5 onwards. Data points within the grey zone are not significantly different from the mixture value at $p \leq 0.05$. Lines connecting data points are for visual aid only.

mixed CC amendments throughout the experiment, maintaining levels comparable to the unamended control at $13.0 \pm 0.17 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$. The buckwheat promoted the highest values observed for a CC amendment, reaching $14.8 \pm 0.46 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ on day 30 and $14.4 \pm 0.69 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ on day 45, but was not significantly different from any other treatment. In contrast, the TSP promoted a steep and consistent increase in NaOH-P_i over time, rising to $34.3 \pm 1.01 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ on day 45. These values were significantly higher than those observed for all other amendments and represented a 2.6-fold increase compared to the unamended control.

The 0.1 mol L^{-1} NaOH extractable organic P (NaOH-P_o , Figure S4) showed significant variability within the treatment replicates. The NaOH-P_o in the unamended control remained constant at an average of $88.1 \pm 0.98 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ through all sampling dates, and no significant differences were produced by any amendment. Among the mixtures, the highest NaOH-P_o increases were produced by the $\text{BO} \pm \text{LS} \pm \text{RT}$ on day 10, which reached $97.5 \pm 2.36 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, an 8.18 mg kg^{-1} average increase

compared to the average of its components. Despite the lack of significant differences, all amendments, including TSP, resulted in numerically higher average NaOH-P_o levels compared to the unamended control.

3.7 | Microbial Biomass P

MBP (Figure S5), that is, the amount of P immobilised in the biomass of soil microorganisms, remained constant in the unamended control treatment throughout the entire incubation period, averaging $15.0 \pm 1.63 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$. All amended soils had numerically higher MBP than the unamended control throughout the incubation period; however, no significant differences were observed across all treatments. On day 5, the mustard exhibited the highest average MBP value of $24.1 \pm 4.57 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, a 62% average increase in comparison to the unamended control. The CC mixtures did not produce significant differences from the unamended control and behaved similarly to their components'

FIGURE 8 | Soil labile P (sum of AER-P, inorganic and organic $\text{NaHCO}_3\text{-P}$, mg kg^{-1}) levels over 45 days following amendment with single cover crop residues and their mixtures at a 60 mg kg^{-1} P dose. The red dashed lines show the average values of the three single crops composing each mixture for comparison. The grey area represents HSD values, facilitating comparisons from day 5 onwards. Data points within the grey zone are not significantly different from the mixture value at $p \leq 0.05$. Lines connecting data points are for visual aid only.

averages. The highest MBP increases were observed for $\text{BO} \pm \text{LS} \pm \text{RT}$ and $\text{LS} \pm \text{PH} \pm \text{BC}$ on day 10, and $\text{BO} \pm \text{BW} \pm \text{MT}$ and $\text{BO} + \text{RT} + \text{MT}$ on days 5 and 10. Additionally, a significant correlation ($R^2=0.82$) was found between MBP and NaOH-P_o when all data derived from CC amended treatments (225 observations) were included, not considering either control (Figure S6).

4 | Discussion

4.1 | Amendment Effects on Soil Carbon and Nitrogen Dynamics

Soils play a critical role in the capture and storage of both organic and inorganic C forms (Schrumpf et al. 2011; Huang et al. 2024). Soil C accumulation has been in the spotlight due to its capacity to mitigate climate change and enhance soil quality (Jastrow et al. 2007), as well as its role in improving soil fertility, water

retention, and agricultural productivity (Lehmann et al. 2020). However, the effect of plant diversity on soil C and N dynamics can be complex and context dependent. Plant diversity can boost C storage (Spohn et al. 2023; Pingthaisong et al. 2024) but may not always impact nutrient cycling, with factors like soil type and climate also playing crucial roles (Cong et al. 2015).

In our experiment, the incorporation of CC residues led to a lower increase in SOC than expected given the high biomass inputs. This discrepancy can be explained by the removal of coarse POM during sieving, which eliminated a key reservoir of organic C in the early stages of decomposition (Schmidt et al. 2011; Lehmann et al. 2020). The removal of coarse POM likely shifted microbial activity towards finer organic matter fractions, accelerating their decomposition and increasing microbial respiration, leading to CO_2 emissions and further C loss. This is corroborated by (Fohrafellner et al. 2024), who concluded that the incorporation of CC residues into cropland affects C pools differently depending on particle size and composition.

These C losses, combined with the significantly higher soil N_t due to mineralisation, resulted in a reduction in the soil C:N ratio for CC mixtures compared to their components' averages. This finding supports our first hypothesis that mixtures reduce the soil C:N ratio by increasing N_t proportionally more than SOC, reflecting the accelerated decomposition of the residues compared to single CCs. Crop residues from different species present contrasting biochemical characteristics (Rezgui et al. 2021). In mixtures, this diversity promotes complementary decomposition dynamics, affecting soil microbial community composition and biomass, and therefore directly impacting C and N cycling (Naeem and Li 1997; Nilsson et al. 2008; Chen et al. 2019).

The reduction in soil C:N ratio has important implications for microbial nutrient acquisition strategies and enzyme production. Lower C:N ratios are typically associated with enhanced N availability in the soil, which can alleviate microbial N limitation (Sinsabaugh et al. 2009; Manzoni et al. 2010). When N is more readily available, microbes can shift their resource allocation towards the production of extracellular enzymes, such as phosphatases, to acquire other limiting nutrients, particularly P (Sinsabaugh et al. 2009, 2013; Lehmann et al. 2020). This explains the observed increase in potential phosphatase activity in CC mixtures, as microbes respond to the increased N availability by investing more energy into P acquisition. Moreover, asynchronous decomposition in mixtures, where low-C:N residues like clover and linseed decompose rapidly and high-C:N residues like buckwheat and phacelia decompose more slowly, supports a sustained microbial activity over time (Nilsson et al. 2008; Chen et al. 2019). This temporal diversity in nutrient release can affect soil pH, stabilise microbial biomass and maintain enzyme production for longer periods, further influencing soil P dynamics, including phosphatase activity, microbial activity, biomass and biomass P, and labile P availability.

4.2 | Amendment Effects on Soil pH

The observed shifts in SOC and N_t can help to explain the contrasting effects of the incorporation of residues of the different CC species on the soil pH over time. Generally, reports on the effects of plant residue amendments on soil pH are contradictory (Butterly et al. 2013), with some studies pointing towards acidification and others towards alkalisation (Pocknee and Sumner 1997; Tang and Yu 1999; Xu and Coventry 2003). In our experiment, most CC amendments promoted soil alkalisation (except black oat) especially in the first third of the incubation period. This is in agreement with reports by other authors (Butterly et al. 2013; Vanzolini et al. 2017). The significant differences found in soil pH in treatments such as buckwheat, mustard, and $BW \pm LS \pm BC$ at later stages in comparison to the unamended control are an important factor governing microbial biomass (Jin and Kirk 2018) and activity (Bååth and Anderson 2003), organic C and N solubility (Kemmitt et al. 2006; Curtin et al. 2016) and mineralisation (Zhang et al. 2020).

Interestingly, most mixtures (except $BO \pm BW \pm MT$) promoted lower alkalisation than the average of their components. Both

the alkalisation effects of mixtures and the non-acidifying effect observed of black oat could be related to litter properties like plant biomass alkalinity (Egwu et al. 2021), concentration of base-forming cations, the degree of decomposition, and ion release patterns (Pocknee and Sumner 1997), all of which have been shown to induce soil pH increases at different intensities. Additionally, early uptake of soil NO_3^- (and co-uptake of H^+) by microbes to decompose plant residues could be a source of soil alkalinity (Weligama et al. 2010). The CC diversity, however, may have contributed to a faster decomposition of the organic material, evidenced by the initial dip in soil C:N ratios by up to 26% observed under mixtures (e.g., $BO \pm LS \pm RT$, $RT \pm PH \pm MT$ and the all-crops mixture). This decomposition generated acidity and buffered pH increases to some extent (Ayiti and Babalola 2022).

Besides the lower initial pH spike, most mixtures also promoted a higher late acidification than their component averages, likely linked to accelerated residue decomposition, which generates acidity as a by-product of microbial activity (Adeleke et al. 2017). Residue composition diversity in mixtures can increase microbial activity, leading to sustained production of organic acids (e.g., carboxylic and phenolic acids) that dissociate, releasing H^+ ions. This diversity may also amplify N cycling, as N-rich residues supply NH_4^+ for nitrification, which releases H^+ , while C-rich residues provide energy for nitrifying microbes (Ayiti and Babalola 2022). In addition, the potentially higher microbial respiration under mixtures may generate more CO_2 , which dissolves in water forming H_2CO_3 , further contributing to potential soil acidification (Johan et al. 2021).

Unlike CC amendments, the initial steep drop in soil pH promoted by TSP ($Ca(H_2PO_4)_2$) can be explained by its acidic nature, which released H^+ according to reaction (1), which was subsequently neutralised from day 15 onwards, according to reaction (2).

4.3 | Amendment Effects on Soil Phosphatase Activity

Amendment characteristics and their effects on soil pH intensely affected the potential activity of phosphatases. A consistent drop in the potential activity of both phosphatase groups was observed under TSP, with ACP_{ASE} being significantly lower than the control on every sampling date. This is explained by the high water solubility of this fertiliser, which does not require hydrolysis. Higher P availability and intracellular P_i content have been shown to inhibit the expression of *PHO* genes in microbes, which encode several phosphate-hydrolysing enzymes including ACP_{ASE} and ALP_{ASE} (Oshima et al. 1996; Dick et al. 2011). This potentially results in a reduction in phosphatase synthesis, secretion, and activity in soils (Nannipieri et al. 2011; Wu et al. 2023). The lower relative ALP_{ASE} reduction (−40%) compared to the ACP_{ASE} reduction (−57%) under TSP compared to the unamended control might indicate a lower sensitivity of ALP_{ASE} to P_i availability, but also suggest that its activity was upregulated due to favourable conditions (increased soil pH).

Our phosphatase results corroborate the findings of Colvan et al. (2001), which concluded that P_i availability generally suppresses phosphatase activity, and that microorganisms respond to increased P_o availability by producing phosphatases to hydrolyse organic P compounds into bioavailable inorganic forms (Janes-Bassett et al. 2022).

For CC-amended soils, the increases in the potential activity of both phosphatases were expected due to the high plant residue inputs, which, serving as a substrate, tend to promote a more active and abundant soil microbial community (Eisenhauer et al. 2010; Janes-Bassett et al. 2022). However, increases were only significant for ALP_{ASE} , with much stronger shifts compared to ACP_{ASE} in CC amended soils, as observed by Sharma et al. (2022). The significantly higher ALP_{ASE} activity and pH decrease over time under mixtures only partially confirm our second hypothesis, as no significantly higher P dissolution was observed in comparison to single crops.

One possible explanation for this observation is the initial increase in pH promoted by most plant amendments, which can decrease the exudation and activity of ACP_{ASE} and increase that of ALP_{ASE} (Dick et al. 2000; Rocabrana, Domene, Preece, et al. 2024). Another reason may be that ACP_{ASE} was less affected by CC residue addition because soil microbes secrete lower levels of this enzyme compared to plant roots. These results reinforce the idea that microbe-secreted ACP_{ASE} plays a relatively minor role in the mobilisation of P from organic matter (Rocabrana, Domene, Matteazzi, et al. 2024), since root activity is a direct source of ACP_{ASE} , while ALP_{ASE} is exclusively secreted by microbes (Hallama et al. 2019).

The higher ALP_{ASE} observed in most mixtures (except BW+PH+BC) when compared to the average of their components can be explained by the richer plant residue diversity in these treatments, which has been shown to increase microbial activity (Shi and Marschner 2014; Drost et al. 2020) and might lead to increased phosphatase secretion and activity. Furthermore, these effects may continuously increase ALP_{ASE} release over time, possibly due to the faster initial decomposition of the clover as one component of this mixture (lower C:N ratio), which promotes a stimulus to microorganisms that is extended beyond the presence of clover residue in the soil (Simpson et al. 2011). It is interesting to notice, however, that the all-crops mixture had comparable phosphatase activity to all other mixtures, indicating that continuously increasing the number of plants in the mixture may not result in sustained increases in the activity of these enzymes.

4.4 | Dynamics of Different P Fractions After CCs Residue Incorporation

4.4.1 | Anion Exchange Resin Extracted P

The shifts in SOC, N_p , pH, and phosphatases, all of which suggest P dissolution and mineralisation from plant residues, resulted in significantly higher available soil P under all amendments within the 45 days of the incubation compared to the unamended control. However, no significant differences in AER-P were observed under mixtures when compared to their

component averages, with occasional and inconsistent oscillations above and below the averages. The AER-P is often associated with the readily bioavailable P, either in the soil solution or easily solubilised in water (Liao et al. 2021).

The similar amounts of AER-P released by mixtures in comparison to single species, despite their greater potential ALP_{ASE} activity, can be explained by several factors. First, the potential activity of phosphatases is determined in a pH buffered solution, which does not reflect the soil pH and, therefore, can overestimate in situ enzyme activity (Tabatabai and Bremner 1969). Second, around $75\% \pm 10\%$ of the total P in plant leaves, roots, and stems is found as the inorganic, highly water-soluble orthophosphate forms HPO_4^{2-} and $H_2PO_4^-$ (Noack et al. 2014), in line with what we found in our experiment. These easily releasable P are solubilised first and saturate the soil solution, which is subsequently buffered by the soil. However, other P_i forms, such as poly- and pyrophosphates, as well as P_o forms such as phosphate monoesters (e.g., phytate), phosphate diesters (nucleotides and phospholipids), and α - and β -glycerophosphates of varying degrees of solubility can also be present in the plant tissue (Wieczorek et al. 2022). These P forms can present moderate to high stability in soils, requiring specific phosphatase enzymes and longer periods of time to decompose, mineralise, and release P (Wieczorek et al. 2022).

Despite this, mixtures displayed contrasting P release rates when compared to single species, which were likely driven by differences in residue decomposition dynamics. The chemical heterogeneity within these mixtures can lead to asynchronous decomposition and P release, where WEP-rich residues like clover stimulate early microbial activity, while residues with lower WEP, such as black oat, decompose more slowly, and delaying microbial responses (Drost et al. 2020; Lehmann et al. 2020).

As discussed, variations in the C:N ratios of the residues across treatments likely played a significant role in shaping microbial dynamics and P release (Shi and Marschner 2014; Shi et al. 2020). Residues with high C:N ratios provide a C-rich but N-poor substrate, which can lead to a temporary immobilisation of P as microbes prioritise N assimilation for their metabolic activities (Zhang et al. 2018). This immobilisation phase can delay P mineralisation, as microbial communities require additional time to degrade more recalcitrant C compounds before releasing nutrients back into the soil. In contrast, residues with lower C:N ratios, such as clover, decompose more readily due to their higher nitrogen content, allowing microbes to metabolise these substrates without a significant need for external nitrogen sources. This rapid decomposition can result in an earlier release of P, followed by a decline as the nutrient becomes depleted or immobilised within microbial biomass. The combination of residues in mixtures likely moderated these extremes, with the diversity of C:N ratios creating a balance between rapid and delayed decomposition.

Another factor could be competition among microbial communities for P, temporarily immobilising the nutrient before releasing it back into the soil. This dynamic cycling could result in short-term variations in P availability that fluctuates above or below the average, depending on the balance between P immobilisation and mineralisation at any given time. Therefore, the

broader range of residue compositions provided by the mixtures led to a more gradual but sustained P release, driven by variations in C:N ratios of its components and microbial stimulus, which explains the mixture's AER-P plateau after day 10. In contrast, the uniform tissue composition by the single crops exhibited sharper peaks in AER-P followed by declines, as the residue-P was rapidly dissolved and potentially fixed in more stable fractions.

The highest AER-P increase (+18.4 mg kg⁻¹) was promoted by TSP on day 5, which, despite being >90% water-soluble, represented only ~30% of the 60 mg kg⁻¹ of P added. If the entire labile P pool is considered (AER-P plus NaHCO₃-P_{i,o}), increases of 29.3 mg kg⁻¹ were promoted by TSP on day 5, ~48% of the total P applied. For CC amended soils, the highest AER-P increment was 11.6 mg kg⁻¹ by the clover on day 15, representing only 19.3% of the total P added. If considering the whole labile pool, P increases of 26.0 mg kg⁻¹ were promoted by the clover on the same day, representing ~43% of the total P applied.

4.4.2 | Amendment Effects on NaHCO₃-P_i and -P_o

Like for AER-P, NaHCO₃-P_i and -P_o were increased by all amendments, but the differences between CCs and TSP mostly disappeared on day 45. This result partially confirms our third hypothesis, as CC amendments promoted higher labile P levels over time when compared to the control, but no differences in labile P were observed between mixtures, single crops, or TSP. Interestingly, however, all buckwheat-containing mixtures showed a singular pattern in which NaHCO₃-P_o was reduced after day 15, falling below the component's averages. Meanwhile, their average NaHCO₃-P_i increased after day 15, albeit without statistical significance. This may suggest a late decomposition of the organic material in these mixtures, likely related to the high C:N ratio of the buckwheat, which possibly took longer to decompose than the other components.

The all-crops mixture also showed a pattern of substantial NaHCO₃-P_o increase from day 15 onwards, resulting in a higher labile P towards the end of the incubation. This can be explained by the complex interactions between the diverse plant residues in the mixture and the soil microbiome (Drost et al. 2020). Specifically, the inclusion of a wider diversity of residues in the all-crops mixture may have fostered complementary biomass decomposition dynamics. For example, the combination of a broader range of CCs with varying C:N ratios could have balanced nutrient release, supporting a delayed and more sustained P_i dissolution and P_o mineralisation. In addition, the heterogeneity in residue characteristics likely stimulated a more diverse and active soil microbial community, enhancing microbial activity and turnover. The diversity and increased complexity of plant materials may have influenced microbial biomass and activity and may have delayed the decomposition of certain residues, leading to a gradual accumulation of NaHCO₃-P_o (Satisha and Devarajan 2005; Audette et al. 2020). In contrast, mixtures containing only three species may have lacked this level of functional diversity, resulting in less pronounced or less sustained increases in labile P over time (Drost et al. 2020).

Labile P values well below the added P dose observed for all treatments can be explained by the soil's P buffering capacity, defined

as the soil's ability to resist solution P concentration changes (Helfenstein et al. 2018; dos Reis et al. 2020; Meng et al. 2022). Higher soil clay content is directly related to its P buffering and binding capacity (Gérard 2016; Mumbach et al. 2021; Xiong et al. 2022). Therefore, despite our Hypothesis (3) positing that CC mixtures would increase soil labile P levels due to their functional diversity and potential for complementary decomposition and nutrient release, the elevated clay content (44%) in the soil used was likely responsible for the lack of differences observed between treatments, as it efficiently buffered P out of the solution into less available fractions. This is evidenced by the simultaneous decrease in labile P and increase in NaOH-P_i under TSP. Since both NaOH-P_i and P_o are often considered constituents of the moderately labile P pool (Liao et al. 2021), shifts can be explained by the addition of different plant residue-derived P forms, as well as phosphate-soil interactions.

4.4.3 | Amendment Effects on Soil NaOH-P_i and -P_o

In our trial, non-WEP forms (such as the ones discussed in Section 4.4.1) accounted for 24%–34% of the total P in the residues. When added to the soil, these plant-derived P forms of lower availability can immediately increase NaOH-P_i and P_o, depending on their nature, which explains increases in both P fractions. Additionally, highly soluble P forms, such as those released by TSP, may also undergo bioavailability reductions over time through strengthening of bonds between P, clay, and Fe- and Al-oxides. Such reactions remove P from the labile pool (Kim et al. 2015), potentially explaining the NaOH-P_i increases observed under the TSP treatment. This increase can have important implications for soil P status long term, as it contributes to the accumulation of P forms of lower availability, representing an inefficiency in fertiliser use as well as a potential source of P losses through erosion and runoff.

4.5 | Amendment Effects on Soil Microbial Biomass P

Crop residue composition plays a critical role in shaping microbial activity and nutrient cycling. Residue diversity also affects microbial community composition, with mixtures promoting a more diverse and active microbial population (Drost et al. 2020). Different plant species provide a variety of C substrates that select for specialised microbial functional groups (Wang et al. 2020; Lehmann et al. 2020). Diverse microbial communities are often associated with higher decomposition rates and nutrient turnover, as different microorganisms specialise in breaking down specific organic compounds (Lange et al. 2015; Drost et al. 2020). However, interactions within microbial communities can also lead to competition for resources, potentially delaying organic material mineralisation. For example, the slower decomposition of high C:N residues may prolong microbial P immobilisation during the early stages of decomposition, temporarily reducing P availability (Pingthaisong et al. 2024). In contrast, low-C:N residues decompose more rapidly, providing a short-term boost to nutrient availability but not sustaining it over time.

Although not statistically significant, the tendency to increased NaOH-P_o observed for most amendments could be partially

attributed to a surge in microbial activity and biomass, due to the high WEP contained in both biomass and TSP, which was immobilised into the microbial biomass (Chen and Xiao 2023). Increases in MBP indicate that P is taken up from the soil by microbes in order to decompose residue-derived C (Brookes 2001; Zhang et al. 2018). It is interesting to highlight that despite the increase in MBP observed under TSP, which suggests microbial uptake and subsequent growth, the potential activity of both phosphatases was nevertheless reduced under TSP due to the great increase in available P_i , as previously discussed.

Microbial biomass carbon (MBC) and microbial activity have been shown to increase after available P additions (Wu et al. 2022) such as CC mixture residues in soils (Drost et al. 2020), but MBC has also been shown to remain steady while microbial activity increases (Shi and Marschner 2014). In our experiment, the lack of significant MBP changes can be explained by three factors. First, while low soil bioavailable P levels can be a limiting factor to the growth and activity of the soil microbial biomass (Wu et al. 2022; Jiang et al. 2024), a study has shown that in a range of bio-physio-chemically different soils, microorganism growth was limited in environments with Olsen-P under 0.7 mg kg^{-1} (Cao et al. 2016). In our study, the baseline soil P level (3.42 mg kg^{-1} Olsen-P) may not have been strongly limiting for microbes, but low enough to promote the exudation and activity of phosphatases. Second, the low number of replicates per sampling date, chosen due to practical constraints, reduced the statistical power of our analysis and increased variability between replicates. Third, this variability is further increased by the limitations of the CHCl_3 -fumigation method, which is known for occasional low result consistency due to the sensitivity of microbial biomass measurements to procedural variability (Mori et al. 2021; Wang and Tang 2024).

Nevertheless, variations in MBP averages in amended soils suggest microbial P immobilisation in the initial stages of incubation. Therefore, MBP can be understood as a moderately labile P pool with no immediate availability but with fast turnover. This is further evidenced by the strong linear correlation of MBP with NaOH-P_o found in our study, similar to that reported by Jin et al. (2013). Furthermore, MBP represented 15%–20% of the NaOH-P_o pool, similar to the MBP fraction on NaOH-P_o reported by Esberg et al. (2010). These findings have potential practical implications for CC systems, as they highlight the microbial effects on P cycling and the potential delays in availability that can be caused by their dynamics. Farmers may consider incorporating CCs with rapid decomposition, such as legumes, which can increase microbial biomass and accelerate P dissolution.

4.6 | Potential P Release Beyond the Experimental Period

Although we only examined a 45-day period, longer incubation studies would likely reveal continued impacts of CC residues on soil P availability due to ongoing decomposition and microbial activity. Slowly decomposing residues could provide continuous P_o mineralisation, while some P_o might be immobilised in microbial biomass or stabilised in SOM, acting as long-term P reservoirs. Higher P_o levels would likely maintain phosphatase activity, facilitating the ongoing conversion of P_o into

bioavailable P_i . The diversity in residue composition, particularly in mixtures, could enhance microbial activity and promote complementary decomposition patterns, ensuring a sustained P release.

However, potential risks such as P leaching, runoff, or the accumulation of less available P forms emphasise the importance of tailored management practices and long-term field studies to fully optimise CC residues for sustainable soil P availability. Under field conditions, factors such as variable weather, soil heterogeneity, fluctuating moisture, and rhizosphere interactions would likely affect decomposition and P cycling (Hallama et al. 2019; Lehmann et al. 2020). For instance, drought or excessive rainfall could impact microbial activity and nutrient release, while active plant roots would compete for nutrients and enhance P mobilisation through exudates or acidification. Furthermore, in contrasting conditions, such as in sandy soils with lower buffering capacities and SOM content, P release from CC residues might result in more pronounced increases in bioavailable P. Similarly, in soils with higher SOM turnover rates or differing pH ranges, the decomposition dynamics and microbial activity might exhibit different trends compared to those observed here (Jiang et al. 2024).

Nevertheless, the results provided in this manuscript can guide farmers in timing CC planting and termination to optimise P release prior to the main cropping season, ensuring that plants have access to sufficient P during critical growth stages. Ultimately, by strategically choosing and managing CCs, farmers can improve soil health, enhance nutrient availability, and promote sustainable agricultural practices that increase crop yields and reduce reliance on mineral fertilisers.

5 | Conclusions

Our results confirm hypothesis (1), as CC mixtures did reduce the C:N ratio in soils, especially in comparison to the controls, indicating accelerated decomposition of the organic material. We also partially confirmed hypothesis (2), since CC mixtures displayed a tendency for increased potential ALP_{ASE} activity in comparison to their component averages and both controls, and promoted a steeper pH decline later in the incubation period in comparison to single crops and the unamended control. Finally, we partially confirm hypothesis (3), as although all amendments increased soil labile P after 45 days incubation, CC mixtures did not promote higher available P levels in comparison to their component averages, single CCs, or the fertilised control.

Overall, in terms of their decomposition and P release rates, six out of the eight CC mixtures performed worse than their most P-release efficient single component, as the residue diversity did not improve soil conditions enough to overcome the negative contributions of their slower decomposing crops to the mixture's effect on P availability. Nevertheless, CC mixtures often promoted lower C:N ratios, ALP_{ASE} activities and a higher late soil acidification compared to the averages of their components. Despite these effects, which indicate enhanced P-solubilising processes, the levels of labile P remained similar across all plant-amended treatments. This is likely due to the slow rate of P release from the CCs, which was insufficient to overcome the soil's

strong capacity to buffer excess P, transferring it to less available pools or immobilising it in microbial biomass.

It is critical, however, to highlight that our experiment only addressed the early stages of biomass decomposition and its P cycling, which, in its entirety, involves other P solubilising effects such as root activity and synergies in shared rhizospheres, as well as long-term impacts on microbial diversity, community, and activity. Therefore, our results help elucidate the biomass decomposition mechanisms in a clayey chernozem soil under a high biomass amount and may not be translatable to other soil types, biomass incubation rates, and environmental conditions. Future studies at field scale, with different soil types and seasonal dynamics, as well as considering different crop species and mixtures, are critical to fully capture the complexity of P dissolution and mineralisation from CCs in soils.

We conclude that, in the conditions of our experiment, incorporated CC mixtures behaved similarly to single crops and their components averages for labile P, but increased it relative to fallow. While CC mixtures may have a higher potential than their single components or single crops in P cycling, the differences would have to come from the higher P exploration and uptake in the CCs growth stage, resulting in litter with a higher P content. These findings contribute significantly to our understanding of CC mixture decomposition patterns in chernozems and may serve as a foundation for future studies on CC mixtures and support farmers in practical decisions.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

References

Adeleke, R., C. Nwangburuka, and B. Oboirien. 2017. "Origins, Roles and Fate of Organic Acids in Soils: A Review." *South African Journal of Botany* 108: 393–406. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sajb.2016.09.002>.

Ågren, G. I., J. Å. M. Wetterstedt, and M. F. K. Billberger. 2012. "Nutrient Limitation on Terrestrial Plant Growth—Modeling the Interaction Between Nitrogen and Phosphorus." *New Phytologist* 194: 953–960. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2012.04116.x>.

Almeida, D. S., D. Menezes-Blackburn, H. Zhang, P. M. Haygarth, and C. A. Rosolem. 2019. "Phosphorus Availability and Dynamics in Soil

Affected by Long-Term Ruzigrass Cover Crop." *Geoderma* 337: 434–443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2018.09.056>.

Audette, Y., D. S. Smith, C. T. Parsons, W. Chen, F. Rezaeezhad, and P. van Cappellen. 2020. "Phosphorus Binding to Soil Organic Matter via Ternary Complexes With Calcium." *Chemosphere* 260: 127624. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.127624>.

Ayiti, O. E., and O. O. Babalola. 2022. "Factors Influencing Soil Nitrification Process and the Effect on Environment and Health." *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems* 6: 821994. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2022.821994>.

Bååth, E., and T.-H. Anderson. 2003. "Comparison of Soil Fungal/Bacterial Ratios in a pH Gradient Using Physiological and PLFA-Based Techniques." *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 35: 955–963. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717\(03\)00154-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(03)00154-8).

Beillouin, D., T. Ben-Ari, E. Malézieux, V. Seufert, and D. Makowski. 2021. "Positive but Variable Effects of Crop Diversification on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services." *Global Change Biology* 27: 4697–4710. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15747>.

Brooker, R. W., F. T. Maestre, R. M. Callaway, et al. 2008. "Facilitation in Plant Communities: The Past, the Present, and the Future." *Journal of Ecology* 96: 18–34. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2745.2007.01295.x>.

Brookes, P. 2001. "The Soil Microbial Biomass: Concept, Measurement and Applications in Soil Ecosystem Research." *Microbes and Environments* 16: 131–140. <https://doi.org/10.1264/jsm2.2001.131>.

Brookes, P. C., D. S. Powlson, and D. S. Jenkinson. 1982. "Measurement of Microbial Biomass Phosphorus in Soil." *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 14: 319–329. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717\(82\)90001-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717(82)90001-3).

Butterly, C. R., J. A. Baldock, and C. Tang. 2013. "The Contribution of Crop Residues to Changes in Soil pH Under Field Conditions." *Plant and Soil* 366: 185–198. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-012-1422-1>.

Calegari, A., T. Tiecher, W. L. Hargrove, et al. 2013. "Long-Term Effect of Different Soil Management Systems and Winter Crops on Soil Acidity and Vertical Distribution of Nutrients in a Brazilian Oxisol." *Soil and Tillage Research* 133: 32–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2013.05.009>.

Cao, H., R. Chen, L. Wang, et al. 2016. "Soil pH, Total Phosphorus, Climate and Distance Are the Major Factors Influencing Microbial Activity at a Regional Spatial Scale." *Scientific Reports* 6: 25815. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep25815>.

Chen, C., H. Y. H. Chen, X. Chen, and Z. Huang. 2019. "Meta-Analysis Shows Positive Effects of Plant Diversity on Microbial Biomass and Respiration." *Nature Communications* 10: 1332. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-09258-y>.

Chen, C., and W. Xiao. 2023. "The Global Positive Effect of Phosphorus Addition on Soil Microbial Biomass." *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 176: 108882. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2022.108882>.

Chen, J., H. Xu, J. Seven, T. Zilla, M. A. Dippold, and Y. Kuzyakov. 2024. "Microbial Phosphorus Recycling in Soil by Intra- and Extracellular Mechanisms." *ISME Communications* 3, no. 1: 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43705-023-00340-7>.

Chen, X., H. Y. H. Chen, and S. X. Chang. 2022. "Meta-Analysis Shows That Plant Mixtures Increase Soil Phosphorus Availability and Plant Productivity in Diverse Ecosystems." *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 6: 1112–1121. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-022-01794-z>.

Colvan, S., J. Syers, and A. O'Donnell. 2001. "Effect of Long-Term Fertiliser Use on Acid and Alkaline Phosphomonoesterase and Phosphodiesterase Activities in Managed Grassland." *Biology and Fertility of Soils* 34: 258–263. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s003740100411>.

Cong, W.-F., E. Hoffland, L. Li, et al. 2015. "Intercropping Enhances Soil Carbon and Nitrogen." *Global Change Biology* 21: 1715–1726. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12738>.

- Curtin, D., M. E. Peterson, and C. R. Anderson. 2016. "pH-Dependence of Organic Matter Solubility: Base Type Effects on Dissolved Organic C, N, P, and S in Soils With Contrasting Mineralogy." *Geoderma* 271: 161–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2016.02.009>.
- Damon, P. M., B. Bowden, T. Rose, and Z. Rengel. 2014. "Crop Residue Contributions to Phosphorus Pools in Agricultural Soils: A Review." *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 74: 127–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2014.03.003>.
- Daughtridge, R. C., Y. Nakayama, and A. J. Margenot. 2021. "Sources of Abiotic Hydrolysis of Chromogenic Substrates in Soil Enzyme Assays: Storage, Termination, and Incubation." *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 158: 108245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2021.108245>.
- de Mendiburu, F. 2023. "agricolae: Statistical Procedures for Agricultural Research." *R package version 1*: 3–7. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=agricolae>.
- Dick, C. F., A. L. A. Dos-Santos, and J. R. Meyer-Fernandes. 2011. "Inorganic Phosphate as an Important Regulator of Phosphatases." *Enzyme Research* 2011: 103980. <https://doi.org/10.4061/2011/103980>.
- Dick, W. A., L. Cheng, and P. Wang. 2000. "Soil Acid and Alkaline Phosphatase Activity as pH Adjustment Indicators." *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 32: 1915–1919. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717\(00\)00166-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(00)00166-8).
- dos Reis, J. V., V. H. V. Alvarez, R. D. Durigan, et al. 2020. "Interpretation of Soil Phosphorus Availability by Mehlich-3 in Soils With Contrasting Phosphorus Buffering Capacity." *Revista Brasileira de Ciência do Solo* 44: e0190113. <https://doi.org/10.36783/18069657rbcs20190113>.
- Drost, S. M., M. Rutgers, M. Wouterse, W. de Boer, and P. L. E. Bodelier. 2020. "Decomposition of Mixtures of Cover Crop Residues Increases Microbial Functional Diversity." *Geoderma* 361: 114060. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2019.114060>.
- Egwu, U., B. Uchenna-Egwu, and G. C. Ezeokpube. 2021. "Ash-Extracts From Plant Residues Can Provide Sufficient Buffering Alkalinity and Trace Elements Required to Prevent Operation Instability to Guarantee Optimum Methane Yield During Anaerobic Digestion of Agricultural Residues." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 318: 128369. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128369>.
- Eisenhauer, N., H. Beßler, C. Engels, et al. 2010. "Plant Diversity Effects on Soil Microorganisms Support the Singular Hypothesis." *Ecology* 91: 485–496. <https://doi.org/10.1890/08-2338.1>.
- Elhakeem, A., W. van der Werf, J. Aja, et al. 2019. "Cover Crop Mixtures Result in a Positive Net Biodiversity Effect Irrespective of Seeding Configuration." *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 285: 106627. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2019.106627>.
- Esberg, C., B. du Toit, R. Olsson, U. Ilstedt, and R. Giesler. 2010. "Microbial Responses to P Addition in Six South African Forest Soils." *Plant and Soil* 329: 209–225. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-009-0146-3>.
- Finney, D. M., and J. P. Kaye. 2017. "Functional Diversity in Cover Crop Polycultures Increases Multifunctionality of an Agricultural System." *Journal of Applied Ecology* 54: 509–517. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12765>.
- Fohrafellner, J., K. M. Keiblinger, S. Zechmeister-Boltenstern, R. Murugan, H. Spiegel, and E. Valkama. 2024. "Cover Crops Affect Pool Specific Soil Organic Carbon in Cropland – A Meta-Analysis." *European Journal of Soil Science* 75: e13472. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.13472>.
- Frøseth, R. B., K. Thorup-Kristensen, S. Hansen, and M. A. Bleken. 2022. "High N Relative to C Mineralization of Clover Leaves at Low Temperatures in Two Contrasting Soils." *Geoderma* 406: 115483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2021.115483>.
- Gérard, F. 2016. "Clay Minerals, Iron/Aluminum Oxides, and Their Contribution to Phosphate Sorption in Soils—A Myth Revisited." *Geoderma* 262: 213–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2015.08.036>.
- Gillis, J. D., and G. W. Price. 2016. "Linking Short-Term Soil Carbon and Nitrogen Dynamics: Environmental and Stoichiometric Controls on Fresh Organic Matter Decomposition in Agroecosystems." *Geoderma* 274: 35–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2016.03.026>.
- Hallama, M., C. Pekrun, H. Lambers, and E. Kandeler. 2019. "Hidden Miners—The Roles of Cover Crops and Soil Microorganisms in Phosphorus Cycling Through Agroecosystems." *Plant and Soil* 434: 7–45. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-018-3810-7>.
- Hansen, V., D. Müller-Stöver, B. Gómez-Muñoz, A. Oberson, and J. Magid. 2022. "Differences in Cover Crop Contributions to Phosphorus Uptake by Ryegrass in Two Soils With Low and Moderate P Status." *Geoderma* 426: 116075. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2022.116075>.
- Hedley, M. J., J. W. B. Stewart, and B. S. Chauhan. 1982. "Changes in Inorganic and Organic Soil Phosphorus Fractions Induced by Cultivation Practices and by Laboratory Incubations." *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 46: 970–976. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1982.03615995004600050017x>.
- Helfenstein, J., J. Jegminat, T. I. McLaren, and E. Frossard. 2018. "Soil Solution Phosphorus Turnover: Derivation, Interpretation, and Insights From a Global Compilation of Isotope Exchange Kinetic Studies." *Biogeosciences* 15: 105–114. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-15-105-2018>.
- Heuermann, D., N. Gentsch, G. Guggenberger, et al. 2022. "Catch Crop Mixtures Have Higher Potential for Nutrient Carry-Over Than Pure Stands Under Changing Environments." *European Journal of Agronomy* 136: 126504. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2022.126504>.
- Honvault, N., D. Houben, C. Nobile, S. Firmin, H. Lambers, and M. P. Faucon. 2021. "Tradeoffs Among Phosphorus-Acquisition Root Traits of Crop Species for Agroecological Intensification." *Plant and Soil* 461: 137–150. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-020-04584-3>.
- Huang, Y., X. Song, Y.-P. Wang, et al. 2024. "Size, Distribution, and Vulnerability of the Global Soil Inorganic Carbon." *Science* 384: 233–239. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adf7918>.
- ISO (International Organization for Standardization). 2019. "Soil Quality - Determination of the Water-Retention Characteristic - Laboratory Methods (ISO 11274:2019)."
- IUSS Working Group WRB. 2015. "World Reference Base for Soil Resources 2014, Update 2015 International Soil Classification System for Naming Soils and Creating Legends for Soil Maps." World Soil Resources Reports No. 106. FAO, Rome.
- Janes-Bassett, V., M. S. A. Blackwell, G. Blair, et al. 2022. "A Meta-Analysis of Phosphatase Activity in Agricultural Settings in Response to Phosphorus Deficiency." *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 165: 108537. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2021.108537>.
- Jansa, J., and A. Hodge. 2021. "Swimming, Gliding, or Hyphal Riding? On Microbial Migration Along the Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Hyphal Highway and Functional Consequences Thereof." *New Phytologist* 230: 14–16. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.17244>.
- Jastrow, J. D., J. E. Amonette, and V. L. Bailey. 2007. "Mechanisms Controlling Soil Carbon Turnover and Their Potential Application for Enhancing Carbon Sequestration." *Climatic Change* 80: 5–23. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-006-9178-3>.
- Jia, Y., V. M. Gray, and C. J. Straker. 2004. "The Influence of Rhizobium and Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi on Nitrogen and Phosphorus Accumulation by Vicia Faba." *Annals of Botany* 94: 251–258. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mch135>.
- Jiang, F., L. Zhang, J. Zhou, T. S. George, and G. Feng. 2021. "Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi Enhance Mineralisation of Organic Phosphorus by Carrying Bacteria Along Their Extraradical Hyphae." *New Phytologist* 230: 304–315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.17081>.

- Jiang, M., K. Y. Crous, Y. Carrillo, et al. 2024. "Microbial Competition for Phosphorus Limits the CO₂ Response of a Mature Forest." *Nature* 630: 660–665. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07491-0>.
- Jin, J., C. Tang, R. Armstrong, C. Butterly, and P. Sale. 2013. "Elevated CO₂ Temporally Enhances Phosphorus Immobilization in the Rhizosphere of Wheat and Chickpea." *Plant and Soil* 368: 315–328. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-012-1516-9>.
- Jin, Q., and M. F. Kirk. 2018. "pH as a Primary Control in Environmental Microbiology: 1 Thermodynamic Perspective." *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 6: 21. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2018.00021>.
- Johan, P. D., O. H. Ahmed, L. Omar, and N. A. Hasbullah. 2021. "Phosphorus Transformation in Soils Following co-Application of Charcoal and Wood Ash." *Agronomy* 11, no. 10: 2010. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy11102010>.
- Joner, E. J., and A. Johansen. 2000. "Phosphatase Activity of External Hyphae of Two Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi." *Mycological Research* 104: 81–86. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0953756299001240>.
- Kassambara, A. 2023. "ggpubr: 'ggplot2' Based Publication Ready Plots." <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/ggpubr/index.html>.
- Kemmitt, S. J., D. Wright, K. W. T. Goulding, and D. L. Jones. 2006. "pH Regulation of Carbon and Nitrogen Dynamics in Two Agricultural Soils." *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 38: 898–911. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2005.08.006>.
- Kim, B., M. Gautier, C. Rivard, C. Sanglar, P. Michel, and R. Gourdon. 2015. "Effect of Aging on Phosphorus Speciation in Surface Deposit of a Vertical Flow Constructed Wetland." *Environmental Science and Technology* 49: 4903–4910. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es506164v>.
- Kim, K., A. Kaestner, M. Lucas, and A. N. Kravchenko. 2023. "Microscale Spatiotemporal Patterns of Water, Soil Organic Carbon, and Enzymes in Plant Litter Detritusphere." *Geoderma* 438: 116625. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2023.116625>.
- Kumar, V., D. Brainard, R. Bellinder, and R. Hahn. 2011. "Buckwheat Residue Effects on Emergence and Growth of Weeds in Winter-Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) Cropping Systems." *Weed Science* 59: 567–573. <https://doi.org/10.1614/WS-D-11-00006.1>.
- Kuzyakov, Y., and E. Blagodatskaya. 2015. "Microbial Hotspots and Hot Moments in Soil: Concept & Review." *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 83: 184–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2015.01.025>.
- Lange, M., N. Eisenhauer, C. A. Sierra, et al. 2015. "Plant Diversity Increases Soil Microbial Activity and Soil Carbon Storage." *Nature Communications* 6: 6707. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms7707>.
- Lehmann, J., C. M. Hansel, C. Kaiser, et al. 2020. "Persistence of Soil Organic Carbon Caused by Functional Complexity." *Nature Geoscience* 13: 529–534. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-020-0612-3>.
- Liao, D., C. Zhang, H. Lambers, and F. Zhang. 2021. "Changes in Soil Phosphorus Fractions in Response to Long-Term Phosphate Fertilization Under Sole Cropping and Intercropping of Maize and Faba Bean on a Calcareous Soil." *Plant and Soil* 463: 589–600. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-021-04915-y>.
- Little, S. A., P. J. Hocking, and R. S. B. Greene. 2004. "A Preliminary Study of the Role of Cover Crops in Improving Soil Fertility and Yield for Potato Production." *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis* 35: 471–494. <https://doi.org/10.1081/CSS-120029726>.
- Liu, J., M. L. Macrae, J. A. Elliott, H. M. Baulch, H. F. Wilson, and P. J. A. Kleinman. 2019. "Impacts of Cover Crops and Crop Residues on Phosphorus Losses in Cold Climates: A Review." *Journal of Environmental Quality* 48: 850–868. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2019.03.0119>.
- Loeppmann, S., E. Blagodatskaya, J. Pausch, and Y. Kuzyakov. 2016. "Enzyme Properties Down the Soil Profile—A Matter of Substrate Quality in Rhizosphere and Detritusphere." *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 103: 274–283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2016.08.023>.
- Manzoni, S., J. A. Trofymow, R. B. Jackson, and A. Porporato. 2010. "Stoichiometric Controls on Carbon, Nitrogen, and Phosphorus Dynamics in Decomposing Litter." *Ecological Monographs* 80: 89–106. <https://doi.org/10.1890/09-0179.1>.
- Meng, C., H. Liu, Y. Li, et al. 2022. "Influence Path Identification of Topography, Soil, Hydrology and Landscape on Phosphorus Buffering Capacity in Typical Agricultural Catchments in Central Subtropical China." *Journal of Environmental Management* 315: 115164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115164>.
- Mori, T., S. Wang, C. Wang, J. Mo, and W. Zhang. 2021. "Is Microbial Biomass Measurement by the Chloroform Fumigation Extraction Method Biased by Experimental Addition of N and P?" *iForest - Biogeosciences and Forestry* 14: 408–412. <https://doi.org/10.3832/IFOR3374-014>.
- Mumbach, G. L., L. C. Gatiboni, D. J. Dall'Orsoletta, et al. 2021. "Refining Phosphorus Fertilizer Recommendations Based on Buffering Capacity of Soils From Southern Brazil." *Revista Brasileira de Ciência do Solo* 45: e20200113. <https://doi.org/10.36783/18069657rbc20200113>.
- Murphy, J., and J. P. Riley. 1962. "A Modified Single Solution Method for the Determination of Phosphate in Natural Waters." *Analytica Chimica Acta* 27: 31–36. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2670\(00\)88444-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-2670(00)88444-5).
- Naeem, S., and S. Li. 1997. "Biodiversity Enhances Ecosystem Reliability." *Nature* 390: 507–509. <https://doi.org/10.1038/37348>.
- Nannipieri, P., L. Giagnoni, L. Landi, and G. Renella. 2011. "Role of Phosphatase Enzymes in Soil." In *Phosphorus in Action: Biological Processes in Soil Phosphorus Cycling*, edited by E. Bünemann, A. Oberson, and E. Frossard, 215–243. Springer.
- Nilsson, M.-C., D. A. Wardle, and T. H. DeLuca. 2008. "Belowground and Aboveground Consequences of Interactions Between Live Plant Species Mixtures and Dead Organic Substrate Mixtures." *Oikos* 117: 439–449. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2007.0030-1299.16265.x>.
- Njeru, E. M., L. Avio, C. Sbrana, et al. 2014. "First Evidence for a Major Cover Crop Effect on Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi and Organic Maize Growth." *Agronomy for Sustainable Development* 34: 841–848. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-013-0197-y>.
- Noack, S. R., M. J. McLaughlin, R. J. Smernik, et al. 2014. "Phosphorus Speciation in Mature Wheat and Canola Plants as Affected by Phosphorus Supply." *Plant and Soil* 378: 125–137. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-013-2015-3>.
- Ntonta, S., I. Mathew, R. Zengeni, P. Muchaonyerwa, and V. Chaplot. 2022. "Crop Residues Differ in Their Decomposition Dynamics: Review of Available Data From World Literature." *Geoderma* 419: 115855. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2022.115855>.
- Olsen, S., C. Cole, F. Watanabe, and L. Dean. 1954. *Estimation of Available Phosphorus in Soils by Extraction With Sodium Bicarbonate*. USDA.
- Oshima, Y., N. Ogawa, and S. Harashima. 1996. "Regulation of Phosphatase Synthesis in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*—A Review." *Gene* 179: 171–177. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1119\(96\)00425-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1119(96)00425-8).
- Pingthaisong, W., S. Blagodatsky, P. Vityakon, and G. Cadisch. 2024. "Mixing Plant Residues of Different Quality Reduces Priming Effect and Contributes to Soil Carbon Retention." *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 188: 109242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2023.109242>.
- Pocknee, S., and M. E. Sumner. 1997. "Cation and Nitrogen Contents of Organic Matter Determine Its Soil Liming Potential." *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 61: 86–92. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1997.03615995006100010014x>.
- Püschel, D., M. Janoušková, A. Voříšková, H. Gryndlerová, M. Vosátka, and J. Jansa. 2017. "Arbuscular Mycorrhiza Stimulates Biological

- Nitrogen Fixation in Two *Medicago* spp. Through Improved Phosphorus Acquisition." *Frontiers in Plant Science* 8: 390. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2017.00390>.
- Raniro, H. R., and J. Santner. 2024. "Differential Phosphorus Acquisition Strategies of Nine Cover Crop Species Grown in a Calcareous and a Decalcified Chernozem." *Plant and Soil* 498: 671–684. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-023-06466-w>.
- Reiss, E. R., and L. E. Drinkwater. 2022. "Promoting Enhanced Ecosystem Services From Cover Crops Using Intra- and Interspecific Diversity." *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 323: 107586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2021.107586>.
- Rezgui, C., I. Trinsoutrot-gattin, M. Benoit, et al. 2021. "Linking Changes in the Soil Microbial Community to C and N Dynamics During Crop Residue Decomposition." *Journal of Integrative Agriculture* 20: 3039–3059. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-3119\(20\)63567-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2095-3119(20)63567-5).
- Rocabrana, P. C., X. Domene, A. Matteazzi, et al. 2024. "Effect of Organic Fertilisation on Soil Phosphatase Activity, Phosphorus Availability and Forage Yield in Mountain Permanent Meadows." *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 368: 109006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2024.109006>.
- Rocabrana, P. C., X. Domene, C. Preece, and J. Peñuelas. 2024. "Relationship Among Soil Biophysicochemical Properties, Agricultural Practices and Climate Factors Influencing Soil Phosphatase Activity in Agricultural Land." *Agriculture* 14, no. 2: 288. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture14020288>.
- Rose, T. J., P. Damon, and Z. Rengel. 2010. "Phosphorus-Efficient Faba Bean (*Vicia Faba* L.) Genotypes Enhance Subsequent Wheat Crop Growth in an Acid and an Alkaline Soil." *Crop & Pasture Science* 61: 1009–1016. <https://doi.org/10.1071/CP10205>.
- Satisha, G. C., and L. Devarajan. 2005. "Humic Substances and Their Complexation With Phosphorus and Calcium During Composting of Pressmud and Other Biodegradables." *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis* 36: 805–818. <https://doi.org/10.1081/CSS-200049454>.
- Schmidt, M. W. I., M. S. Torn, S. Abiven, et al. 2011. "Persistence of Soil Organic Matter as an Ecosystem Property." *Nature* 478: 49–56. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10386>.
- Scholz, R. W., A. E. Ulrich, M. Eilittä, and A. Roy. 2013. "Sustainable Use of Phosphorus: A Finite Resource." *Science of the Total Environment* 461–462: 799–803. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.05.043>.
- Schrumpf, M., E. D. Schulze, K. Kaiser, and J. Schumacher. 2011. "How Accurately Can Soil Organic Carbon Stocks and Stock Changes Be Quantified by Soil Inventories?" *Biogeosciences* 8: 1193–1212. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-8-1193-2011>.
- Sharma, S., S. Kaur, O. P. Choudhary, et al. 2022. "Tillage, Green Manure and Residue Retention Improves Aggregate-Associated Phosphorus Fractions Under Rice–Wheat Cropping." *Scientific Reports* 12, no. 1: 7167. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-11106-x>.
- Shi, A., and P. Marschner. 2014. "Changes in Microbial Biomass C, Extractable C and Available N During the Early Stages of Decomposition of Residue Mixtures." *Soil Research* 52: 366–372. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR13128>.
- Shi, Y., N. Ziadi, C. Hamel, et al. 2020. "Soil Microbial Biomass, Activity and Community Structure as Affected by Mineral Phosphorus Fertilization in Grasslands." *Applied Soil Ecology* 146: 103391. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2019.103391>.
- Simpson, R. J., A. Oberson, R. A. Culvenor, et al. 2011. "Strategies and Agronomic Interventions to Improve the Phosphorus-Use Efficiency of Farming Systems." *Plant and Soil* 349: 89–120. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-011-0880-1>.
- Sinsabaugh, R. L., B. H. Hill, and J. J. Follstad Shah. 2009. "Ecoenzymatic Stoichiometry of Microbial Organic Nutrient Acquisition in Soil and Sediment." *Nature* 462: 795–798. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature08632>.
- Sinsabaugh, R. L., S. Manzoni, D. L. Moorhead, and A. Richter. 2013. "Carbon Use Efficiency of Microbial Communities: Stoichiometry, Methodology and Modelling." *Ecology Letters* 16: 930–939. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12113>.
- Soltangheisi, A., A. P. B. Teles, L. R. Sartor, and P. S. Pavinato. 2020. "Cover Cropping May Alter Legacy Phosphorus Dynamics Under Long-Term Fertilizer Addition." *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 8: 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2020.00013>.
- Spohn, M., S. Bagchi, L. A. Biederman, et al. 2023. "The Positive Effect of Plant Diversity on Soil Carbon Depends on Climate." *Nature Communications* 14, no. 1: 6624. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-42340-0>.
- Tabatabai, M. A., and J. M. Bremner. 1969. "Use of p-Nitrophenyl Phosphate for Assay of Soil Phosphatase Activity." *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 1: 301–307. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717\(69\)90012-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-0717(69)90012-1).
- Tang, C., and Q. Yu. 1999. "Impact of Chemical Composition of Legume Residues and Initial Soil pH on pH Change of a Soil After Residue Incorporation." *Plant and Soil* 215: 29–38. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1004704018912>.
- Teles, A. P. B., M. Rodrigues, W. F. Bejarano Herrera, et al. 2017. "Do Cover Crops Change the Lability of Phosphorus in a Clayey Subtropical Soil Under Different Phosphate Fertilizers?" *Soil Use and Management* 33: 34–44. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sum.12327>.
- Vanzolini, J. I., J. A. Galantini, J. M. Martínez, and L. Suñer. 2017. "Changes in Soil pH and Phosphorus Availability During Decomposition of Cover Crop Residues." *Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science* 63: 1864–1874. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03650340.2017.1308493>.
- Varela, M. F., M. Barraco, A. Gili, M. A. Taboada, and G. Rubio. 2017. "Biomass Decomposition and Phosphorus Release From Residues of Cover Crops Under no-Tillage." *Agronomy Journal* 109: 317–326. <https://doi.org/10.2134/agronj2016.03.0168>.
- Vitousek, P. M., S. Porder, B. Z. Houlton, and O. A. Chadwick. 2010. "Terrestrial Phosphorus Limitation: Mechanisms, Implications, and Nitrogen–Phosphorus Interactions." *Ecological Applications* 20: 5–15. <https://doi.org/10.1890/08-0127.1>.
- Vogeler, I., M. Böldt, and F. Taube. 2022. "Mineralisation of Catch Crop Residues and N Transfer to the Subsequent Crop." *Science of the Total Environment* 810: 152142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.152142>.
- Wang, Y., L. Liu, J. Yang, et al. 2020. "The Diversity of Microbial Community and Function Varied in Response to Different Agricultural Residues Composting." *Science of the Total Environment* 715: 136983. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.136983>.
- Wang, Y., and D. W. S. Tang. 2024. "Soil Chemical Fumigation Alters Soil Phosphorus Cycling: Effects and Potential Mechanisms." *Frontiers in Plant Science* 15: 1289270. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2024.1289270>.
- Weligama, C., C. Tang, P. W. G. Sale, M. K. Conyers, and D. L. Liu. 2010. "Application of Nitrogen in NO₃–Form Increases Rhizosphere Alkalinisation in the Subsurface Soil Layers in an Acid Soil." *Plant and Soil* 333: 403–416. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-010-0356-8>.
- White, K. E., E. B. Brennan, M. A. Cavigelli, and R. F. Smith. 2022. "Winter Cover Crops Increased Nitrogen Availability and Efficient Use During Eight Years of Intensive Organic Vegetable Production." *PLoS One* 17: e0267757. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0267757>.
- Wieczorek, D., B. Żyszka-Haberecht, A. Kafka, and J. Lipok. 2022. "Determination of Phosphorus Compounds in Plant Tissues: From Colourimetry to Advanced Instrumental Analytical Chemistry." *Plant Methods* 18: 22. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13007-022-00854-6>.

- Wickham, H., W. Chang, L. Henry, et al. 2024. "ggplot2: Create Elegant Data Visualisations Using the Grammar of Graphics." Retrieved from. <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>.
- Wickham, H., R. François, L. Henry, and K. Müller. 2020. "dplyr: A Grammar of Data Manipulation." *R Package Version 0*, no. 8: 4. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=dplyr>.
- Wu, Q., S. Zhang, Y. Zhao, et al. 2023. "Effects of Initial Carbon-Phosphorus Ratio on Phosphatase, and Phosphorus Availability in Sludge Composting." *Bioresource Technology* 382: 129192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2023.129192>.
- Wu, W., F. Wang, A. Xia, et al. 2022. "Meta-Analysis of the Impacts of Phosphorus Addition on Soil Microbes." *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 340: 108180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2022.108180>.
- Xiong, J., Z. Liu, Y. Yan, et al. 2022. "Role of Clay Minerals in Controlling Phosphorus Availability in a Subtropical Alfisol." *Geoderma* 409: 115592. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2021.115592>.
- Xu, R. K., and D. R. Coventry. 2003. "Soil pH Changes Associated With Lupin and Wheat Plant Materials Incorporated in a Red-Brown Earth Soil." *Plant and Soil* 250: 113–119. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1022882408133>.
- Yu, H.-Y., W.-X. He, Y.-N. Zou, M. D. Alqahtani, and Q. S. Wu. 2024. "Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi and Rhizobia Accelerate Plant Growth and N Accumulation and Contribution to Soil Total N in White Clover by Difficultly Extractable Glomalin-Related Soil Protein." *Applied Soil Ecology* 197: 105348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2024.105348>.
- Zhang, L., X. Ding, Y. Peng, T. S. George, and G. Feng. 2018. "Closing the Loop on Phosphorus Loss From Intensive Agricultural Soil: A Microbial Immobilization Solution?" *Frontiers in Microbiology* 9: 104. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.00104>.
- Zhang, X., J. Guo, R. D. Vogt, et al. 2020. "Soil Acidification as an Additional Driver to Organic Carbon Accumulation in Major Chinese Croplands." *Geoderma* 366: 114234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2020.114234>.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.